

INFLUENCE OF CELEBRITY ENDORSEMENT ON CONSUMERS' PATRONAGE OF HEINEKEN LAGER BEER AMONG RESIDENTS IN ENUGU METROPOLIS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14283685>

Abstract: *This study focused on Influence of Celebrity Endorsement on Consumers' Patronage of Heineken lager beer among Residents in Enugu Metropolis. The study was guided by three objectives namely; to determine the percentage of Heineken Lager Beer consumers in Enugu Metropolis who are aware of celebrity endorsements of the product, to quantify the extent to which celebrity endorsement influences the frequency and quantity of Heineken Lager Beer consumption among consumers in Enugu Metropolis and to identify the associated challenges on celebrity endorsement of Heineken lager beer in Enugu metropolis. The study was anchored on Rational Choice Theory and the research design adopted was survey research design. The population of the study is residents of Enugu metropolis. The population of the study is 660991 obtained from 2016 projection of the National Bureau of Statistics website. Sample size of 399 was obtained using Taro Yamane formula for determining sample size. To ensure fair representation, Heineken lager beer drinkers in the Enugu metropolis were chosen at random from several strata using the purposive sampling technique. The study found that most consumers of Heineken lager beer in Enugu metropolis are not familiar with the brand ambassadors, as they are not usually well-known celebrities. However, celebrity endorsement significantly influences adult consumption of Heineken beer, often driven by peer pressure and imitation. Additionally, the study revealed that celebrity endorsement has negative social consequences, including increased school dropouts, academic failures, and anti-social behaviors among adults in Enugu metropolis. The researcher recommends that to enhance the effectiveness of Heineken's celebrity endorsements, the brand should increase consumer awareness through targeted campaigns and ensure that the celebrities they select align with the values of their target audience, regular consumer feedback surveys will help assess the success of these endorsements, allowing for adjustments where necessary. Additionally, Heineken should diversify its promotional strategies by incorporating influencer marketing and local ambassadors alongside celebrity endorsements. Finally, addressing potential challenges, such as negative publicity involving endorsers, will help protect the brand's image and maintain consumer trust.*

Keywords: *Celebrity Endorsement, Consumers' Patronage, Heineken Lager Beer, advertisement*

1.1 Background to the Study

In the contemporary business environment, companies face the constant challenge of distinguishing their products and services from the competition in a crowded marketplace. A fundamental approach to achieving this differentiation is through advertising, which serves as a powerful tool for creating brand awareness, fostering consumer loyalty, and driving sales. Advertising can take various forms, including traditional media like print and television, as well as modern digital platforms. In industries such as beer production, advertising plays a significant role in shaping public perception and influencing consumer purchasing decisions.

The beer industry, in particular, is highly competitive, with companies like Heineken employing diverse marketing tools such as print ads, TV commercials, digital platforms, and promotional events to boost brand visibility and engage consumers. One of the most prominent trends in advertising in recent years is the use of celebrity endorsements. Celebrity endorsement involves leveraging the popularity and influence of well-known personalities to promote a brand or product. The emotional and psychological connection that consumers often have with celebrities makes this strategy particularly effective in attracting consumers, especially when celebrities have a broad and loyal following.

In fact, celebrity endorsements have become an essential marketing strategy for companies across various industries, including the beer sector. By associating their products with famous personalities, brands like Heineken can appeal to both a broader and younger demographic. This is because celebrity-endorsed advertising not only enhances a brand's image but also makes it more relatable and aspirational for consumers. The strategic use of celebrities helps brands connect with consumers on an emotional level, influencing their purchasing decisions and fostering brand loyalty.

Advertising is central to the success of any product. Without sufficient advertising, even the best products may fail to reach their intended market, as potential consumers may not be aware of their existence or uses. As Strain (2019) notes, the ultimate goal of any producer is to identify a market that can sustain the sales and consumption of their products. Advertising plays a key role in achieving this goal by persuading and motivating consumers to make a purchase. In many cases, advertisers use celebrities as the face of their campaigns, capitalizing on the celebrity's reputation and charisma to attract consumer attention. This form of celebrity endorsement can be seen in various advertising media, from billboards to TV commercials, digital platforms, and print publications (Ellison, 2020).

One of the cores aims of an advertising campaign is to capture and hold the attention of potential customers. Marketers often face the challenge of crafting an engaging and memorable campaign that will appeal to a diverse audience. Celebrity endorsements have been shown to be an effective tool in this regard, as they can grab consumers' attention and help create positive associations with the product being advertised. As Agbo (2021) highlights, when consumers encounter multiple advertising messages across different media, celebrity endorsements stand out as a particularly effective way to create lasting impressions.

The emotional impact of celebrity endorsements on consumers cannot be overstated. Many consumers transfer their admiration for a celebrity to the product they are endorsing, often without realizing it. As Hensel (2018) suggests, consumers are likely to unconsciously believe that if a celebrity endorses a product, it must be of high quality. The visual representation of celebrities in advertisements evokes positive emotions and generates unconscious preferences for the product. This emotional connection can significantly influence consumer behavior, leading to increased brand loyalty and patronage (Oracle, 2020).

However, not all celebrity endorsements are equally effective. Celebrity endorsements can backfire if the chosen celebrity is not a good fit for the product or brand. According to Hawkins (2011), many celebrity endorsements fail because marketers choose celebrities based on personal preferences or emotional connections, rather than on their relevance to the product being advertised. If the celebrity has no meaningful connection to the product, consumers may become distracted by the celebrity, undermining the message the brand is trying to convey.

The beer industry in Nigeria, like other sectors, has witnessed the proliferation of various brands over the years. Once dominated by a few brands, the market is now crowded with breweries producing millions of hectoliters of beer under various brand names, including Heineken, Guinness, Star, and Harp, among others (Mitchel & Tomo, 2021). Heineken, in particular, has experienced tremendous growth in Africa, with beer consumption reaching 14.7 million kiloliters in 2022, a 5.2 percent increase from the previous year. This growth is fueled by both the increasing popularity of Heineken as a premium beer brand and its strategic use of advertising and celebrity endorsements. In Nigeria, Heineken has become one of the leading beer brands, particularly in Enugu State, where consumption rates have significantly increased (Ucheigwe, 2023).

Nigeria Breweries Ltd., the producer of Heineken, has made extensive use of celebrity endorsements in its advertising campaigns. The company's strategic use of Nigerian celebrities, particularly in beer advertisements, has contributed to its success in building a strong consumer base and fostering brand loyalty (Ndolo, 2016). One notable example is Jidenna Theodore Mobisson, a Nigerian-American musician who has served as Heineken's brand ambassador since 2015. Jidenna's association with Heineken has helped strengthen the brand's appeal, particularly among younger, trend-conscious consumers. Heineken's collaboration with Jidenna has also contributed to its image as a global brand that resonates with Nigerian culture, as the singer frequently highlights the brand's global presence and relevance to Nigerian consumers (Bellanaija, 2017).

The effectiveness of celebrity endorsements for Heineken can be attributed to the brand's strategic messaging and the alignment of its celebrity ambassador with the values and image the brand seeks to project. As Anazia (2017) notes, Jidenna's partnership with Heineken promotes family values and cultural connections, which has helped to foster a deeper emotional bond between the brand and its Nigerian consumers. Additionally, Heineken's strong market presence, as evidenced by its extensive

distribution network and sales figures, suggests that the brand's use of celebrity endorsements has been a key factor in its continued success.

According to Hensel (2018) customers may be manipulated via positioning what they want to look, sense or hear, at the right time, within the right location and on the first-class way with a view to create a fantastic effect in them. Heineken lager beer with celebrity endorsement can most effectively acquire interest whilst such is perceived as having an awesome pleasant appeal by purchasers,

In Enugu Metropolis, as in other regions, advertising and celebrity endorsements significantly influence consumer preferences and behaviors. The residents are exposed to a wide range of advertising content, much of which leverages the popularity of celebrities to create positive associations with products like Heineken Lager Beer. This research seeks to explore how celebrity endorsement affects consumers' patronage of Heineken Lager Beer among residents in Enugu Metropolis, providing insights into the effectiveness of this advertising strategy in the local market. **1.2 Statement of the Problem**

The use of celebrity endorsement has become a dominant marketing strategy, especially in industries like beer, where companies such as Heineken leverage the popularity of celebrities to enhance their brand identity. While the practice is widespread, there remains a need for further investigation into its effectiveness in influencing consumer behavior and fostering long-term brand loyalty. This study aims to assess whether celebrity endorsements have led to increased patronage of Heineken Lager Beer among residents of Enugu Metropolis, or if other factors are more significant in shaping consumer decisions.

One of the primary motivations for this research is the growing concern over the return on investment (ROI) in celebrity endorsements. Heineken spends considerable resources on marketing campaigns featuring celebrities, but there is limited empirical evidence showing that these campaigns directly contribute to increased sales and consumer loyalty in Nigeria, particularly in Enugu Metropolis. The study seeks to determine if the influence of celebrities justifies the financial investment or if Heineken should explore alternative advertising methods.

Additionally, the success of celebrity endorsements depends on factors such as the celebrity's credibility, relevance to the product, and their appeal to the target audience. A mismatch between the celebrity and the product could undermine the effectiveness of the endorsement. Furthermore, negative events in a celebrity's personal life may tarnish the brand's image, potentially leading to consumer backlash.

The rise of digital marketing and social media has also altered the marketing landscape. Younger consumers are increasingly drawn to online influencers and peer recommendations, which may diminish the effectiveness of traditional celebrity endorsements in television and print media. Given this shift, it is crucial to evaluate whether celebrity endorsements still hold the same power in influencing purchasing decisions for Heineken Lager Beer in Enugu Metropolis.

Overall, this study aims to determine the actual impact of celebrity endorsements on consumer patronage of Heineken Lager Beer. By assessing the effectiveness of this marketing strategy in the local market, the research will offer valuable insights into whether Heineken's reliance on celebrity figures has been successful or if alternative promotional strategies should be considered.

1.3 Objectives of study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the influence of celebrity endorsement on consumers' patronage of Heineken Lager Beer among residents of Enugu Metropolis. Specifically, the study aims to:

1. Determine the percentage of Heineken Lager Beer consumers in Enugu Metropolis who are aware of celebrity endorsements of the product.
2. Quantify the extent to which celebrity endorsement influences the frequency and quantity of Heineken Lager Beer consumption among consumers in Enugu Metropolis.
3. identify the associated challenges on celebrity endorsement of Heineken lager beer in Enugu metropolis

1.4. Research Questions

1. What percentages of consumers of Heineken Lager Beer in Enugu Metropolis are aware of celebrity endorsements of the product?
2. To what extent does celebrity endorsement influence the frequency and quantity of Heineken Lager Beer consumption among consumers in Enugu Metropolis?
3. What are the associated challenges on celebrity endorsement of Heineken lager beer in Enugu metropolis?

1.5 Hypotheses

This study will be guided by the following null hypotheses

1. **H01:** There is no significant relationship between consumer awareness of celebrity endorsements and their patronage of Heineken Lager Beer among residents of Enugu Metropolis.
2. **H02:** Celebrity endorsement does not significantly influence the drinking behaviors of Heineken Lager Beer consumers in Enugu Metropolis.
3. **H03:** There are no significant challenges associated with celebrity endorsements of Heineken Lager Beer as perceived by consumers in Enugu Metropolis.

Review of Related Literature

2.1.1 Concept of Celebrities

In this study, a celebrity is defined as an individual with a high-profile public position, typically in fields such as sports, politics, leadership, or entertainment (Mberia, 2018). Roll (2016) views celebrities as well-known figures in film, music, sports, or politics. McCracken (2018) describes them as individuals who command significant public influence. Celebrity endorsement refers to these figures using their public platform to promote products (Sparredal, 2019).

Erdogan (2018) highlights that celebrities possess distinct traits such as likability, attractiveness, and unique abilities that make them stand out in society. The use of celebrities in advertisements has become increasingly common, with studies showing that 20 to 25 percent of all ads feature them (Brown, 2016). The popularity of celebrity endorsements is based on the belief that they lead to more favorable ad ratings and product evaluations (Silvera & Austad, 2017). Additionally, Erdogan (2018) suggests that celebrity endorsements can significantly increase a business's financial returns.

Companies often use celebrities to increase brand visibility, launch new products, or reposition existing ones. According to Lutz, McKenzie, and Belch (2017), in today's competitive market, celebrity endorsements are an effective way to gain product recognition. Ahmed (2014) asserts that celebrity endorsements help businesses reach relevant audiences and enhance their competitive edge. Even with the occasional negative press surrounding certain celebrities, Shimp (2018) argues that celebrity endorsements continue to be a powerful advertising tool.

However, Mberia (2020) warns that businesses must account for the high costs associated with celebrity endorsements. While some companies may fail to maximize their potential, Apejaye (2020) argues that, when managed well, celebrity endorsements can significantly boost brand equity and improve a product's position in the market. While these endorsements can provide short-term benefits such as greater market share and increased awareness, they come with high costs and competition (Chatzibeis, 2021).

Celebrity endorsements carry inherent risks, including negative publicity or scandals involving the celebrity, which could harm the brand's reputation (Dimed & Joulyana, 2019). Despite these risks, the alignment between the celebrity and the brand is often more important than the celebrity's physical attractiveness. Brands may choose less conventionally attractive celebrities if they better embody the brand's image and values.

2.1.2 The Concept of Advertising

Advertising is defined as a paid, non-personal form of publicity that promotes ideas, products, or services through mass media like visual, verbal, and text channels (Anyanwele, 2017). It aims to influence consumer behavior and perceptions towards a product or brand (Kotler et al., 2018). Advertising can leave a lasting impression on consumers, educating them about products and shaping their decisions over time. The content and delivery of the advertisement are crucial for achieving these goals (Royo-Vela, 2015). Research shows that consumers are more likely to favor a product if they enjoy the advertisement's message (Homer, 2019).

Celebrity endorsements are often used in advertising as they are believed to enhance effectiveness. Consumers tend to associate the qualities of a celebrity with the product they endorse, influencing their purchase decisions. Panchayat (2018) notes that advertisements frequently employ psychological techniques, including the use of celebrities, to persuade consumers. Classical conditioning is one such method used to shape attitudes through advertising (Stuart, Shimp, & Egle, 2018).

2.1.3 Alcohol Advertising and Promotion

The promotion of alcohol plays a significant role in its consumption patterns, influencing both market dynamics and consumer behavior (Holder, 2017). Alcohol advertising is vital for companies to maintain relevance and market share, especially as the industry faces stiff competition. The youth demographic is a key target for alcohol advertisements, though measuring the precise impact of such ads can be challenging. However, the advancement of technology has made alcohol advertising more pervasive (Jenigan, 2017). Regulatory frameworks for alcohol marketing have largely remained unchanged since the early 20th century.

2.1.4 Beer Business in Nigeria

The beer industry is a key sector in Nigeria's economy, representing about 96% of all alcoholic beverage sales and contributing significantly to the manufacturing value-added (MVA) sector (Ukaegbu, 2013). Despite socio-economic challenges, the Nigerian beer market continues to thrive, with a large consumer base of drinking-age individuals. The sector has transitioned from a duopoly to an oligopoly, with multinational companies such as Heineken, Guinness, and SABMiller competing for market share. The beer market benefits from the prohibition of beer imports, supporting local production, and the tax breaks provided to indigenous brewers (Ukaegbu, 2013).

Heineken leads the market with a 71% share through its subsidiary Nigerian Breweries, while Guinness and SABMiller control smaller portions. The Nigerian beer industry has shown consistent growth, with a compound annual growth rate of about 5.6% from 2011 to 2020, despite challenges like rising living costs and distribution issues. The sector's long-term prospects remain strong, driven by the growing middle class and the ongoing demand for beer (Futurelearn, 2022).

2.1.5 Concept of Consumer Patronage

Consumer patronage refers to the consistent purchasing behavior of a customer, indicating loyalty to a specific product or brand (Oliver, 2017). It is also understood as the support or encouragement a customer provides to a business in exchange transactions, such as repeatedly visiting or purchasing from a store. For businesses, especially in competitive sectors like banking, it is crucial to meet customer needs to ensure loyalty (Sulek, 2022). When customers are satisfied with a product, they tend to make repeated purchases. Research suggests that mental processes play a key role in fostering customer loyalty, with consumers using products to solve various problems, which strengthens preferences and encourages recurrent business.

2.1.6 Concept of Consumer Behavior

Consumer behavior encompasses the choices and actions that individuals take when purchasing or using a product (Futurelearn, 2022). It includes the entire process, from the initial purchase decision to product use and potential future repurchase. The buying process is often seen as a cycle, including

acquisition, use, and disposal (Arnoud, 2018). The consumer decision model identifies seven steps in the decision-making process: need recognition, information search, pre-purchase evaluation, purchase, consumption, post-consumption evaluation, and divestment (Blackwell, 2019). These steps are influenced by various factors, including internal and external influences, which marketers study to understand how they affect consumer decisions.

2.1.7 Factors Influencing Consumer Buying Behavior

Consumer buying behavior is influenced by a variety of factors, both internal and external. Internal factors include personal preferences, psychological motivations, and past experiences, while external factors include cultural, social, and environmental influences. External influencers, such as social media and influencers, play a significant role in shaping consumer decisions. Social media platforms, like Instagram, allow influencers to share product recommendations, which can drive purchases, especially when these influencers are aligned with the target market's behaviors. Successful promotional efforts can lead to product purchases, even if the product was not initially considered by the consumer. However, excessive or aggressive advertising can lead to consumer disengagement, especially in the context of social media marketing.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Rational Choice Theory

Rational Choice Theory is a sociological framework that explains social and economic phenomena by focusing on individual decision-making. It posits that people act logically by weighing the benefits and costs of their actions. Individuals make decisions based on their preferences, which are guided by the goal of maximizing their utility. According to this theory, actions are influenced by available information, resources, and constraints. American sociologist Edmond Hoyle developed the theory in 2015, emphasizing that decisions are driven by a calculated assessment of the most beneficial choice, within the bounds of personal resources and societal constraints.

Basic Assumptions of Rational Choice Theory

1. People make decisions by weighing the pros and cons.
2. Decisions are based on the available facts.
3. Personal preferences determine actions.
4. A person chooses from available alternatives.
5. The collective actions of society reflect individual decisions.

Justification of the Theory

Rational Choice Theory suggests that consumer behavior towards Heineken lager beer is influenced by a rational calculation of the costs and benefits of purchasing the product, rather than the celebrity endorsing it. The consumer's decision is driven by the tangible benefits derived from the product, rather than celebrity influence.

Relevance to the Study

Rational Choice Theory helps explain consumer decisions, such as why individuals may choose Heineken lager beer over other options based on personal preferences and available information. It is used in this study to assess whether celebrity endorsement influences beer consumption, or if consumer choices are primarily based on rational evaluation of product benefits and costs.

2.3 Empirical Review

Eunice (2016) examined the effect of celebrity endorsement on the Ghanaian telecommunication companies on consumers' buying behavior. The study adopted a quantitative research design. The findings of the study indicates that majority of the respondents know much about their brand ambassador. Meanwhile, some of the respondents maintain that branding is all about logo, image and slogan. The study further reveals that celebrity endorsement has significant effect on the consumer patronage of the product. More so, the study indicates that celebrity endorsement has significant positive and significant impact with customer buying behavior.

Emodi (2019) researched on the celebrity endorsement on consumer patronage of locally processed rice in Nigeria, specifically, in South East Nigeria. The study adopted survey research design with a total of six milling rice industries were utilized in Abakiliki Ebonyi state. The findings of the study indicates that image, brand name and brand identity have significant impact on consumer patronage of locally processed rice in Nigeria.

Yatundu, Abuga, and Olala (2017) investigated how public sugar production companies in Kenya performed in response to celebrity endorsements. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to evaluate the data, and the results showed that the performance of public sugar companies was positively and significantly impacted by brand name and image.

Harcourt and Mac-Kingsley (2019), researched on the influence of celebrity endorsement on customer patronage of table water firm in River state Nigeria reveal that brand celebrity has a significant influence on the store traffic flow. The study further indicates that the brand celebrity programme has a significant influence on the referrals.

The study conducted by Kalu, Anyanwu, Maduenyoghasi, and Udo (2016) investigated the impact of celebrity endorsement on the marketing strategies of Nigerian soft drink bottling companies. The research design used in the study was survey. Descriptive tables and the Pearson Correlation Coefficient of the SPSS package were used to analyze the data, and the results indicate that a sizable portion of the total soft drink products marketed annually are extended brands of their parent items.

Dolatabadi (2018) explored the effect of celebrity endorsement on product sale through celebrity endorsement. The study uses Cosmetic product retailers as a case study. According to the study, equity is the major criteria to developing customers trust and loyalty among potential customers. Equity ensures leverage which does not incorporate inequality or preferential treatment from customers and extended boundaries. The study indicates that there is a strong correlation between product equity and consumer loyalty and trust among customers.

Zhang (2019) examined the impact of celebrity endorsement on consumer patronage, the study identified that real satisfaction of the consumer has been the motivating factor inducing people to consume a product and not the celebrity that is endorsing the product. The study further reveals that there are numerous numbers of literatures which support the assertion. Meanwhile, through customer satisfaction, the consumer of the product-built loyalty towards a particular brand that have direct impact on them.

Ogba and Tan (2019) explored the impact of celebrity endorsement on consumer loyalty and commitment in China. The study adopted several analytical techniques such as ANOVA, regression and correlation analysis were employed. The findings of the study indicate that brand image has significant impact on the consumer commitment and loyalty of the product.

A related study on the function of celebrity endorsement in Ghana's telecom sector was carried out by Yeboah (2018). Their research revealed a statistically negligible association between trademarks and network preference, suggesting that trademarks have little effect on mobile network sales. Though not the most crucial element in the telecom sector, the study did discover that brand quality has a considerable impact on mobile network sales in Ghana.

Knox and Balmer, (2016) examine the corporate identity, corporate branding and corporate marketing through the fog, according to the study, top management in organizations don't always understand the power of branding except recently that they have incorporated in their organizational goals because of the competition in the market places. Individuals use branding to distinguish it from another product.

Okwany (2016) carried out a study on the impact of service assortment on the consumers' choice of a product using bar selection as a case study. The study found out that a product that has variety of its associated option is expected to have many customers. The study while explaining the potential behavior of bar patronage indicated that customer's behavior falls short of providing a valid represented sample since it was based on one bar factory patronage.

Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study adopts a survey research design to examine the influence of celebrity endorsement on consumers' patronage of Heineken lager beer among residents in Enugu Metropolis. Survey design is considered appropriate for this study because it allows for the collection of data from a large population in a relatively short time.

3.2 Area of the Study

Enugu metropolis comprises of three local government areas; namely, Enugu East, Enugu North and Enugu South. Enugu metropolis according to the National Population Census (2006) has about 66099 residents in the region.

3.3 Population of the Study

The population of the study is Enugu state with focus on residents of Enugu metropolis. The total population was from 2016 projection of the National Bureau of Statistics website 660991. The population growth was estimated using an annual growth rate of 2.2%. (NBS, 2016)

Enugu Metropolis	Population
Enugu North	244852

Enugu South	137050
Enugu East	279089
Total	660991

3.4 Sample Size

To determine the sample size, the researcher employed Taro Yamane's (1964) formula. For a finite population, the following formula is required:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n= Desired sample size

N= the entire population

e= level of significance or limit of tolerable error assumed to be 5% or 0.05

I= unit, constant figure

Therefore

$$N = \frac{660991}{1 + 660991(0.05)^2}$$

N = 399

3.5 Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling method was adopted by the researcher. In order to select and contact suitable participants for surveys using the purposive sampling strategy, researchers must be aware of the goal of their investigations beforehand.

Enugu Metropolis consists of three local governments and the researcher sampled the respondents in clusters based on their geographic areas.

Stage One: The respondents were classified according to their local government areas.

Enugu East

Enugu North

Enugu South

Stage Two: The respondents were classified according to their communities in their local government areas.

Local government area	Communities
Enugu North	GRA, Ogui, Asata, New Haven, Independence Layout, Ogbete and Iva Valley.
Enugu East	Abakpa, Trans-Ekulu, Nike and Emene.
Enugu South	Achara Layout, Ugwuyi, Maryland, Awkanaw, Obiagu(Ogui New layout) and Uwani.

Stage Three: The researcher randomly selected two communities from each local government area.

Enugu North: Independence Layout and New Haven

Enugu East: Emene and Trans-Ekulu.

Enugu South: MaryLand and Achara Layout.

Stage Four: The copies of the questionnaire shared in each community was determined by way of quota sampling technique

Enugu Urban Local Governments	Bar Visited	Number of Questionnaire Shared
Enugu North	Bush Bar	44
	Ataino Bar	44
	City Hangout	44
Enugu South	Niko Hotel	44
	Nza Joint	44
	Toscana	44
Enugu East	Nike lake	44
	New Berris	45
	Dragon	45

Stage Five: The researcher distributed 399 questionnaire copies in each of the selected local governments.

3.6 Description of Research Instrument

The questionnaire and direct interview for the study comprised two sections, the first contains psychographic data namely; the respondents' occupation, gender, age bracket and educational qualification. The second section inquired for demographic data and consists of fifteen questions on a likert scale of strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree, strongly disagree. The researchers used closed questions.

3.7 Validation of Instrument

The questionnaire was given to experts in the field of communication to evaluate whether the questionnaire effectively captures the topic under investigation.

3.8 Reliability of the Instrument

The Crombach Alpha reliability instrument was used to determine the instrument's reliability. In the states of Emene, New Haven, and Uwani in Enugu, the instrument was given to twenty respondents. The Crombach Alpha reliability test yielded a value of 0.75.

3.9 Method of Data Collection

The researchers administered all the 399 copies of the questionnaire to the respondents in selected areas in Enugu state. The researchers deemed primary method of data collection apt for the study because it was empirical research, hence the information needed was obtained from the structured questionnaire which was distributed and collected by the researchers and also through the in-depth interview method adopted by the researchers.

3.10 Method of Data Analysis

Simple descriptive analysis was used to infer meaning from the data in the table for clarity.

Result Presentation

Table 23: Hypotheses one

H₀: There is no significant relationship between consumer awareness of celebrity endorsements and their patronage of Heineken Lager Beer among residents of Enugu Metropolis.

One-Sample Test

Null Hypothesis	Test Value = 0					
	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
There is no significant relationship between consumer awareness of celebrity endorsements and their patronage of Heineken Lager Beer among residents of Enugu Metropolis.	0.035	379	.011	0.03300	0.021	0.302

Source: SPSS Computation 2024

From the test of hypothesis above using one sample test t-statistics, based on the decision rule, accept null hypothesis if the value of the t-statistics is greater than 0.05, from the result; the value of the t-statistics (0.035) is less than 0.05 hence we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is significant correlation between the level of awareness created by celebrities' endorsement of Heineken lager beer and the patronage of the beer among residents of Enugu metropolis.

DECISION RULE

If the probability (or significant) of the t-calculated is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis but if otherwise, we do not reject the null hypotheses.

Decision: There significant relationship between consumer awareness of celebrity endorsements and their patronage of Heineken Lager Beer among residents of Enugu Metropolis.

Table 24: Hypotheses Two

H₀: Celebrity endorsement does not significantly influence the drinking behaviors of Heineken Lager Beer consumers in Enugu Metropolis.

One-Sample Test

Null Hypothesis	Test Value = 0					
	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper

Celebrity endorsement does not significantly influence the drinking behaviors of Heineken Lager Beer consumers in Enugu Metropolis.	0.013	379	.041	0.00130	0.12	0.34
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Source: SPSS Computation 2024

From the test of hypothesis above using one sample test t-statistics, based on the decision rule, accept null hypothesis if the value of the t-statistics is greater than 0.05, from the result; the value of the t-statistics (0.013) is less than 0.05 hence we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that Celebrity endorsement significantly influenced the drinking behaviors of Heineken Lager Beer consumers in Enugu Metropolis.

DECISION RULE

If the probability (or significant) of the t-calculated is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis but if otherwise, we do not reject the null hypotheses.

Decision: Celebrity endorsement significantly influenced the drinking behaviors of Heineken Lager Beer consumers in Enugu Metropolis.

Table 25: Hypotheses Three

H₀: There are no significant challenges associated with celebrity endorsements of Heineken Lager Beer as perceived by consumers in Enugu Metropolis.

One-Sample Test

Null Hypothesis	Test Value = 0					
	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
There are no significant challenges associated with celebrity endorsements of Heineken Lager Beer as perceived by consumers in Enugu Metropolis	0.033	379	.041	0.00130	0.66	0.44

Source: SPSS Computation 2024

From the test of hypothesis above using one sample test t-statistics, based on the decision rule, accept null hypothesis if the value of the t-statistics is greater than 0.05, from the result; the value of the t-statistics (0.033) is less than 0.05 hence we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there are

significant challenges associated with celebrity endorsements of Heineken Lager Beer as perceived by consumers in Enugu Metropolis.

DECISION RULE

If the probability (or significant) of the t-calculated is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis but if otherwise, we do not reject the null hypotheses.

Decision: There are significant challenges associated with celebrity endorsements of Heineken Lager Beer as perceived by consumers in Enugu Metropolis.

Discussion of Results

The result of the study was aimed at finding the influence of celebrity endorsement of consumers' patronage of Heineken lager beer among residents in Enugu metropolis.

From the result of the first research question, it was discovered that consumers of Heineken lager beer are not interested in knowing the beer brand ambassador, majority of the Heineken lager beer consumers do not know the brand ambassador, Heineken lager beer brand ambassador are not popularly known by consumers of the product, Heineken lager beer brand ambassador is not known by the consumers. The results generally align with the research conducted by Patrick and Lawrence (2016), which used Benin City as a case study to investigate the perceived influence of celebrity endorsement on transportation businesses in Nigeria. The analysis's findings demonstrated that factors influencing consumer preference for the transport firms examined included comfort and safety, brand perception, fare prices, the ability of the drivers and the caliber of the cars, and welfare and customer services.

Also, the result of the instruments in the second research questions supports that celebrity endorsement increases the desires of the adult to drink of Heineken lager beer, Peer pressure and imitation of the celebrity by adult promotes the intake of the Heineken lager beer, the rate at which adult drinks Heineken lager beer due to the influence of the celebrities is highly significant, adults are encouraged to take more Heineken lager beer through celebrity endorsement. This is supported by the work of Ogba and Tan (2019) which examined the effects of celebrity endorsement on customer loyalty and commitment in China. In the study, the relationship between customer commitment and loyalty did not test positive.

The result of the third research question indicates that celebrity endorsement of Heineken lager beer has increased the rate of school dropout amongst the adult in Enugu metropolis, it has increased the rate of antisocial behavior such as rape amongst residents of Enugu metropolis, it has increased the level of academic failures among adults in Enugu metropolis. Celebrity endorsement of Heineken has helped in promoting nuisance and economic/political unrest among the Enugu residents. This finding supports the work of Zhang, (2015) which assessed the Impact of celebrity endorsement on Consumer Behavior. The perceived and real satisfaction of customers has been long linked with the brand image of a product or an organization.

Conclusion

From the analyses of the findings in the research work, the researcher concludes that to a great extent, consumers of Heineken lager beer in Enugu metropolis are aware of the beer brand endorsed by celebrity, there is influence of celebrity endorsement on patronage of Heineken lager beer among residents of Enugu metropolis, celebrity endorsement influences adult into drinking Heineken lager beer against the prescription of the law among residents of Enugu metropolis, problems that arise because of celebrity endorsement of Heineken lager beer among residents of Enugu metropolis are significant.

Recommendations

Having conducted this research and analyzed the field data, the researcher recommends the following points.

- 1. Increase consumer awareness of celebrity endorsements:** Heineken should strengthen its marketing efforts by increasing the visibility of celebrity endorsements through various media platforms to ensure that consumers in Enugu metropolis are well-informed about the association between the brand and its endorsers.
- 2. Enhance the influence of celebrity endorsement on consumer behavior:** Heineken should select celebrities whose personalities and lifestyles resonate with the preferences of the target audience. This will ensure that the endorsements have a significant positive impact on consumers' drinking behaviors, leading to increased patronage.
- 3. Address challenges associated with celebrity endorsement:** Heineken should regularly evaluate the effectiveness of their celebrity endorsements and be prepared to address potential challenges, such as negative public perception of the endorsers or market saturation. This will ensure that celebrity endorsements remain a beneficial marketing strategy for the brand.

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